

Present Energy Scenario and Potentiality of Wind Energy in Bangladesh

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Abstract : Scarcity in energy sector is a major problem, Which can hamper the growing development of a country. Bangladesh is one of the electricity-deprived countries, however, The energy demand of Bangladesh is increasing day to day. Due to the shortage of natural resources and environmental issues, Many nations are now moving towards renewable energy. Among various form of renewable energy, Wind energy is one of most potential source. In this paper, The present energy condition of Bangladesh is discussed and the necessity of moving towards renewable energy is clarified. The wind speed found at different locations at different heights and different years from the survey of several organizations are presented. Although the results of installed low capacity wind turbines (from few kW to few tens of kW) operated by private or government organization in different places in Bangladesh are not so encouraging, however, it is shown that Bangladesh has a high potential of using large wind turbine (MW range) for capturing wind energy at different places. The present condition of wind energy in Bangladesh and other countries in the world are also presented to emphasize the requisite of moving towards wind energy.

Keywords : Renewable energy, Wind speed, Wind power, Modern wind turbine, Scarcity of power, Gas crisis.

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014